

20NRM04 MetrIAQ

D4: Guideline with recommendations on the customised design and dimensioning of the ERM, including the uncertainty of the numerical model developed for the prediction of the emission rate. The numerical model will (i) support the customised generation of the ERM (ii) simulate the transport processes inside the ERM and the compound release into test chamber air and (iii) enable the prediction of the emissions for each of the selected target VOC

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Due date of the deliverable: 30 April 2024

Submission date of the deliverable: 03 July 2024

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1 Introduction

This manuscript has been prepared as part of the work package 2. This work package aimed to develop a suitable FEM model which would describe the emission process from the ERM into the emission test chamber. The current deliverable provides some recommendations on the customised design and dimensioning of the ERM, and includes the uncertainty of the numerical model developed for the prediction of the emission rate.

The FEM model here presented, contains a series of improvements over a similar model produced during the project ENV56 KEY-VOCs. The scope of the ERM model changed during the development of the project, since the geometry and configuration of the ERM passed from embedded VOC sources in homogeneous material to a powder impregnated with VOC. Hence, the current model does not represent physically all the transport phenomena involved in the emission from the material, however an aggregated diffusion coefficient has been implemented. All the modelling was performed in Comsol Multiphysics, version 6.2 (COMSOL AB, Sweden) using solver for the transport of diluted species (*chds*). As it was found out in the EMRP project ENV56 KEY-VOCs [1, 2] inclusion of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) modelling of the gas dynamics in the test chamber does not bring any significant improvement of the modelling results in comparison to the case, where chamber air/gas was replaced by a boundary air/gas layer of thickness of few millimetres. Therefore, the model has been improved and setup to describe the ERM and a stationary air/gas layer (of the prescribed thickness) around the ERM only.

2 Methodology

2.1 FEM Model

The model was adapted from the model of the previous project ENV56 KEY-VOCs [1, 2]. It describes the diffusion of VOC in ERM and its emission of VOC from the top surface of the ERM into the air/gas layer with the prescribed thickness above the ERM. The diffusion of VOC of concentration c_1 [mol.m⁻³] in the ERM material is characterised by diffusion constant D_{mat} [cm².s⁻¹]. In the modelling in the project ENV56 KEY-VOCs it was found, that the air in the chamber may be effectively taken into account with a millimetres thin layer of air around the ERM and thus no fluid flow is needed to be simulated with CFD.

The diffusion of VOC of concentration c_2 [mol.m⁻³] in the air layer of the thickness d_{air} is characterised by diffusion constant D_{air} [cm².s⁻¹]. The convection in that air layer was not taken into account.

The ratio of the concentrations between the c_2 and c_1 is characterised by the partition coefficient K , which is defined as

$$K = \frac{c_2}{c_1} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

If equation (1) would be directly implemented, there would be the discontinuity in the concentration across the boundary, therefore the interaction of the two computational VOC domains with concentrations c_1 and c_2 was implemented by the stiff-spring method using the equation

$$q = M (Kc_1 - c_2), \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

where q [mol.m⁻²s] is the flux of the VOC from the ERM into the air/gas or at the border of the ERM or at the border of the air/gas (due to continuity of the flux they three are the same),

$$-D_{mat} \nabla c_1 = q = -D_{air} \nabla c_2, \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

and M [m/s] is a so-called stiff-spring velocity describing the dynamic behaviour of VOC concentration at the interface between ERM and air/gas layer (1/ M is a surface resistance to the transfer of the VOC from one medium into another). It is invented due to the numerically stiff system at the boundary between the ERM and the air. The M should be enough great value, that equation (2) is automatically enforced. Such a procedure is known from modelling dialysis [5] and from modelling of oxygen consumption and cell viability [6]. In both references value $M = 10\,000$ was used. So, parameter M was not varied in our study, but it was taken with the value of 10 in all of the simulations. We proved, that a higher value does not introduce any change in comparison to the one we used.

In order to capture the experimental setup the model is a 3-dimensional axisymmetric model. The scheme of its setup is presented in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of 3D axisymmetric FEM model without CFD.

Somewhat artificial boundary condition with fixed concentration from the previous model was replaced with a new scalar variable $c_{ch}(t)$ - the average concentration of the VOC in the chamber. It is not a locally-dependent, but a time-dependent variable, which is taken as the outer boundary condition.

This boundary condition is calculated with the implicit equation:

$$n_{VOC,ch}(t) = c_{ERM,0} \cdot V_{ERM} - c_{ERM,ave}(t) \cdot V_{ERM} - \int_0^t n_{VOC,ch}(t') \cdot n_{exch} dt', \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

where:

$n_{VOC,ch}$	Total amount of VOC in the test chamber air	[mol]
$c_{ERM,0}$	Initial concentration of VOC in ERM material	[mol.m ⁻³]
$c_{ERM,ave}$	Average concentration of VOC in ERM material	[mol.m ⁻³]
V_{ERM}	Volume of the sample	[m ³]
n_{exch}	Exchange rate of the air in the chamber	[s ⁻¹]

The first term on the right-hand side of Eq. (4) represents the initial total amount of the VOC in the ERM, i.e. all initially loaded/impregnated VOC into the ERM. The second term represents the amount of the VOC in the ERM at the time t , i.e. the concentration of VOC, which remains in the ERM up to the time t and did not yet evaporate out of the sample. Thus first two terms of Eq. (2) would represent all the VOC in the air of the chamber at the time t if there was no ventilation of air/gas in the chamber. Due to the ventilation, which is described by the last term of Eq. (2), the impregnated air/gas is leaving the chamber. The integrand from this term represents the amount of VOC, which leaves the chamber per unit of time. With the integration in time (from time 0 up to the present moment), the total amount of VOC, that has left the chamber, is obtained.

If Eq. (4) is divided by the total volume of the air/gas in the chamber $V_{ch} - V_{ERM}$, one obtains:

$$c_{ch}(t) = \left(c_{ERM,0} - c_{ERM,ave}(t) \right) \cdot \frac{V_{ERM}}{V_{ch} - V_{ERM}} - n_{exch} \int_0^t c_{ch}(t') dt', \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

where V_{ch} is the volume of the chamber in [m³].

Eq. (5) is re-written in the form

$$g(c_{ch}(t)) \equiv \left(c_{ERM,0} - c_{ERM,ave}(t) \right) \cdot \frac{V_{ERM}}{V_{ch} - V_{ERM}} - c_{ch}(t) - n_{exch} \int_0^t c_{ch}(t') dt' = 0, \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

which was implemented in Comsol Multiphysics as a "global constraint". It is a condition/constraint, which does not apply to each point of the model, i.e. Eq. (6) was not solved in each node of the numerical model, but applies as a global equation for the whole model. Thus our physical problem is in a way distributed,

because we have to solve the equations for $c_1(r, z, t)$ and $c_2(r, z, t)$ for each r and z and on another side global, because we have to solve $c_{ch}(t)$, which is independent on the location, but has fixed zero initial condition $c_{ch}(t=0)=0$.

Our problem was solved with the formalism of Lagrange multipliers introducing function $L = c_{ch} - \lambda g$, whereas with c_{ch} the potential of the main physical problem is symbolically described and λ is a Lagrange multiplier. Derivatives of the L according to c_{ch} and λ were considered, whereas the built-in Comsol variational functionality was used for handling the physical potential equation for that goal. We had to be careful that the time steps were small enough due to the integration in the constraint.

A "User-controlled" "Extremely fine" "Free Quad" mesh with a maximum element size of 0.000195 m, minimum element size of 0.000000039 m, curvature factor of 0.2 and resolution of narrow regions of 1 was taken into account for the geometry. The number of elements is 3724 for the case of a 2 mm thick d_{air} . "Physics-controlled" time steps for the time domain were used with an absolute tolerance factor of 0.01, with "Intermediate Steps taken by solver", "Automatic Maximum step constraint", "Event tolerance" of 0.01, implicit solver type, BDF method with a maximum of 2 and minimum of 1 BDF order and "Nonlinear controller". To imitate the experimental procedure according to EN 16516 the simulation time of 28 days was chosen. The comparison in SER resulting values was performed between results after the 7th, 14th and 28th day of the simulations. The emission rate of the ERM is calculated as the drop of concentration in the ERM, whereas the specific emission rate (SER [$kg \cdot m^{-2} \cdot s^{-1}$]) is the emission rate divided by the surface area of the ERM [1, 2] – see Eq. (7)

$$SER \left[\frac{kg}{m^2 \cdot s} \right] = \frac{d \int c dV [kg]}{dt [s] A [m^2]} \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

2.2 Metrological evaluation methodology

Although the FEM model developed is a dynamic model that predicts the emission profile over time, the measurand considered for the evaluation is the concentration in the chamber after 7 days, in $mol \cdot m^{-3}$.

The uncertainty of the measurand was evaluated through an uncertainty budget based on GUM recommendations. The influence quantities considered in the evaluation, together with the source of the reference value and uncertainties are reported in **Table 1**.

2.2.1 Physical parameters in the model and their uncertainty

In **Table 1** the description of the different physical and numerical parameters, the source of data and their variational interval are described.

Table 1. Reference parameter values origin and origin of the variation of parameters in the parametric study.

Parameter	Source of the reference value and uncertainty	Variational interval
Diffusion constant of VOC in material D_{mat} [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]	<p>Rounded average obtained from regression of experiments D9, D18, D19, D22 and D28 (experiments are presented in the Results section).</p> <p>Uncertainty described in attachment 7.2.2)</p>	From one order of magnitude lower to one order of magnitude higher values.
Partition coefficient K [/]	Value rounded based on the previous experimental data used [1, 2]. Not included in the uncertainty budget since it is not a variable for the case studies under consideration.	From 3 orders of magnitude lower (SVOC) values to 3 orders of magnitude higher values.
Initial concentration in ERM c_0 [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$]	Rounded average value from experiments. Expression and uncertainty described in attachment 7.2.2)	From one order of magnitude smaller values to 5 times higher values
Thickness of air layer d_{air} [mm]	Value from previous project [1, 2]. Not included in the uncertainty budget since it is not a variable for the case studies under consideration.	From order of magnitude smaller values to slightly above the values used in previous project [1,2]
Diffusion constant of VOC in air D_{air} [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]	Value from [3] for hexane. Uncertainty based on the same reference.	From about one order of magnitude smaller values to one order of magnitude higher values (taken into previous project [1, 2] and [4])
Volume of chamber V_{ch} [m^3]	Value from emission chamber characteristics. Uncertainty based on supplier information.	Based on standard capacities, from 5 L to 1 m^3 .
Exchange rate of air in chamber n_{exch} [h^{-1}]	Value from experiments. Experimental uncertainty based on emission chamber information.	From one order of magnitude lower values to one order of magnitude higher values.
Diameter of specimen d_{ERM} [mm]	Rounded average value from experiments. Uncertainty based on measurement instrument used.	From about factor of two lower values to about factor of 2 higher values.
Height of specimen h_{ERM} [mm]	Average value from experiments. Uncertainty based on measurement instrument used.	From about factor of two lower values to about factor of magnitude higher values.

Molar mass of VOC $M_{VOC} [g \cdot mol^{-1}]$	Value for hexane. Constant value from the literature, uncertainty considered 0.	Rounded values from lightest to heaviest gases.
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The air pressure in the chamber was not taken into account in the numerical analysis, the temperature was taken as 20 °C when varying the parameters for uncertainty budget determination.

It is worth mentioning, that assuming a constant D_{mat} is a simplification that applied to the ERM characteristics as expected at the beginning of the project. This was having a homogeneous material with embedded VOC sources inside. The current ERM consists of a free powder with particles that are irregular in shape and size. This translates into different modelling requirements, and challenges the application of only one D_{mat} for describing the transport phenomena.

2.2.2 Sensitivity coefficients estimates

In the FEM problem, 11 different parameters are considered. Different values of each of them were investigated in the present parametric study. They are presented in **Table 2**. Reference values are marked in red (for parameter M , the reference value was 10). The initial concentration of VOC in the chamber was taken as 0 for all the simulations.

Table 2. Reference parameter values and values of the variation of parameters in the parametric study.

Parameter	Values						
Diffusion constant of VOC in material $D_{mat} [cm^2 \cdot s^{-1}]$	10^{-9}	3×10^{-9}	6×10^{-9}	10^{-8}	3×10^{-8}	6×10^{-8}	10^{-7}
Partition coefficient $K [/]$	10^{-7}	10^{-6}	10^{-5}	10^{-4}	0.001	0.01	0.1
Initial concentration in ERM $c_0 [mol \cdot m^{-3}]$	100	500	800	1000	1300	2500	5000
Thickness of air layer $d_{air} [mm]$	0.5	1	1.5	2	3	4	5

Diffusion constant of VOC in air D_{air} [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.0763	0.1	0.3	0.8
Volume of chamber V_{ch} [m^3]	0.005	0.02	0.1	0.27	0.5	1	2
Exchange rate of air in chamber n_{exch} [h^{-1}]	0.05	0.1	0.25	0.5	1	2.5	5
Diameter of specimen d_{ERM} [mm]	10	20	30	35	40	50	70
Height of specimen h_{ERM} [mm]	2	3	4	5	10	20	30
Molar mass of VOC M_{VOC} [$\text{g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$]	20	50	70	86.18	100	120	150

3 Results

3.1 Metrological analysis

An uncertainty budget based on the parameters and data described in Section 2 has been developed. The current uncertainty budget is based on the use of the K parameter applicable for VOCs (not for SVOCs). Over the value 10^{-5} , K does not influence the concentration of the chamber anymore, hence it has been excluded from the uncertainty budget. **Table 3** reports the uncertainty budget for experiment D19.

Table 3. Uncertainty budget of reference case study: Experiment D19

X	Units X	X	$u(X)$	$u(x)$	u_c^2
D_{mat}	$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	9.5E-09	8.80E-09	93%	1.94E-11
C_0	$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^3$	482	322	67%	4.14E-11
D_{air}	$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	0.0763	0.0076	10%	2.32E-22
V_{ch}	m^3	0.270	0.002	0.7%	0
n_{Exch}	h^{-1}	0.500	0.015	3%	1.07E-12
d_{ERM}	Mm	28	1	4%	9.30E-22

h_{ERM}	Mm	3.5	1	29%	1.87E-21
M_{VOC}	g.mol ⁻¹	86.18	0	0%	0
C(7 days) mol.m⁻³		5.7E-06	7.9E-06	138% (k=1)	

The values of uncertainty associated to each influence quantity have different sources. D_{air} value and its uncertainty were taken from literature. The uncertainties of the test chamber volume (V_{ch}), the number of the exchanges in the test chamber (n_{Exch}), molar concentration of the sample (c_0), diameter of the petri dish (d_{ERM}) and height of the sample (h_{ERM}) are based on the experimental available information.

The uncertainty of the molar concentration of the sample is investigated and reported in attachment 7.2.2.

For the D_{mat} uncertainty, an evaluation was performed, based on the regression results of the model over experimental data, minimizing the least squares of the concentration over time curve around day 7 (See attachment 7.2.37.2).

The influence quantities with the most important contributions to the uncertainty for the current setup are c_0 (66.9%), the D_{mat} (31.3%) and the n_{Exch} (1.7%). D_{mat} is currently directly calculated from regression while the n_{Exch} depends on the test chamber used during the test (see **Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Current distribution of uncertainty contributions to C(7 days)

The current distribution of uncertainty can be improved to obtain values compatible with typical uncertainties of experimental molar concentrations (around 25 %) if the uncertainty of D_{mat} is reduced down to 15 % and that of c_0 is narrowed down to 6%. This could be performed by evaluating statistically the

uncertainty of D_{mat} over a significant number of regression points ($> 10^4$) and by improving the reproducibility of loading processes and sample preparation

3.2 Validation of the model and D_{mat} estimation

The D_{mat} for simulations was estimated by means of the least squares method. A range of experimental data from day 5 to day 10 of emission, was compared with simulated data generated using different D_{mat} values.

The $D_{mat_D19} = 9.46 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2.\text{s}^{-1}$ was taken into account for the simulation of the validation experiments. Below, **Table 4** reports the case studies used for validation. The details on regression data for D_{mat} , validation data and methods are available in Attachment 7.2.1

Table 4. Simulation case studies for validation.

Experiment	Material	VOC	Height of sample [mm]	Diameter of sample [mm]
D9	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	5	36
D18	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	2.33	34.5
D19	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	3.49	28
D22	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	2.34	34.5
D28	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	2.34	34.5

The results from the validation are shown in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Results of validation numerical simulations based on selected case studies

Experiment	Time after the beginning [days]	Experimental value in chamber after one week [mol.m ⁻³]	Numerical value in chamber after one week [mol.m ⁻³]	Difference between experiment and numerics
D9	6.93	4.136×10^{-6}	2.568×10^{-6}	-37.9 %
D19 (reference)	6.83	5.711×10^{-6}	5.652×10^{-6}	-1.0 %
D18	6.81	6.285×10^{-6}	8.441×10^{-6}	+34.3 %

D22	6.84	7.191×10^{-6}	8.361×10^{-6}	+16.6 %
D28	7.01	10.97×10^{-6}	7.953×10^{-6}	- 27.5 %

Figure 3 contains a plot based on the results from the validation of the FEM model, using the case studies described above and in **Tables 16** and **17**. In the plot, the experimental results with their uncertainties are included, together with the corresponding simulated values and model uncertainty. Since all the experiments included refer to the same ERM (Hexane – BEA), the experimental average has been represented as a continuous line, while the standard deviation is represented by a dotted line.

The results show an agreement with experimental data without noticeable biases. A *t*-student test at a 95 % significance level confirms that the points formed by the 5 experiments and the simulated points of D9, D18, D19, D22 and D28 belong to the same normal distribution.

Figure 3. Validation of FEM Model vs experimental values.

4 Recommendations on the ERM design

Based on the design experience and the models produced during the development of the model, some recommendations are provided, intended to facilitate the design of ERM to fit the requirements of the different applications.

- Ensure the design of the ERM takes place when the Biot number is over the thresholds recommended ($Bi > 1000$). This ensures that diffusion is the controlling phenomenon, so an appropriate profile of emission can be generated. As a general rule, smaller chambers with higher reproducible velocities are recommended (i.e. rotating plate). See attachment 7.3 for detailed information on how to calculate the Biot number.
- Ensure that for powder supports, a controlled distribution of particle size is maintained, as it affects the reproducibility of samples (e.g. particularly

important that for materials such as activated charcoal a sieving process is included to maintain a more or less reproducible particle size distribution).

- Including a diffusion vial with a trace VOC during development, as it provides a stable reference material for control. It is important that the substance generated does not compete with the VOC being emitted, as this will introduce inaccuracies to the predicted emission. This can be obtained by using a molecule whose size and polarity make less likely the adsorption to the particles of ERM and consequent diffusion. More research in this regard is recommended, both for design purposes and for improvement of the uncertainty evaluation. Attachment 7.3 includes a description of the diffusion vial and the references applicable to the design.
- Improve the uncertainty of D_{mat} , c_0 , and n_{Exch} by target uncertainties, as reported in section 3.1. This will provide predictions with uncertainty comparable with experiments.
- Improve the definition of the measurand by including in the D_{mat} the interparticle and intraparticle diffusivity: Following an evaluation of the Knudsen number, it was determined that transport within the pore size of some of the materials (e.g. zeolites and activated charcoals) could not be properly evaluated by means of a continuous model in the mesoscale (such as the current FEM). The appropriate methods for this kind of system would include molecular simulations coupled with FEM, a type of model that was out of the scope of the work package. In order to improve the capacity of simulation of the different scenarios, would be important to develop a multiscale model that includes all the potential phenomena, such as the Knudsen diffusion, capillarity during the impregnation process and any other phenomena in the microscale.
- Perform experiments with different material-VOC combinations, as a way to estimate the values of D_{mat} for each selected VOC, since right now, the prediction is limited to case studies with known D_{mat} (Hexane + BEA).
- Improve the D_{mat} uncertainty evaluation by performing statistical analysis such as Monte Carlo. There is a high computational cost, however the D_{mat} is an important source of uncertainty with the current setup.
- Improve the reproducibility of the impregnation process and conduct an in-depth analysis of the sources of uncertainty of the process. At present, the concentration within the sample is the greatest source of uncertainty. A major contribution to the c_0 uncertainty is the loading percentage which is strictly connected to the impregnation process and the capacity to quantify the VOC contained in the sample over time.

5 Conclusions

This guideline intends to provide information about the FEM numerical model developed within the WP2, and the uncertainty associated with the prediction of the molar concentration of VOC in the emission test chamber after 7 days of emission. The manuscript also includes a series of recommendations on the design, performance and accuracy of the modelling of the ERM.

The numerical model and accompanying parameters documented in this deliverable, are intended to predict the concentration profiles of ERMs composed of BEA zeolite impregnated with Hexane when tested at atmospheric pressure and ambient temperature. Due to the challenges with the generation of prototypes, other combinations of material/VOC were not tested. In this sense, any deviations in temperature, material or VOC from the base case study would have to be subject to a series of experiments to provide regression data for the calculation of the effective diffusion coefficient of the material (D_{mat}), which is an intrinsic characteristic of the material, dependent on the temperature.

The current manuscript includes also an assessment of the uncertainty of the FEM numerical model developed for the prediction of the emission rate. The most influential quantities have been identified: the concentration in the sample, the effective diffusion coefficient and the number of exchanges in the test chamber. Some target uncertainties have been proposed to decrease the uncertainty of the prediction down to values comparable with experimental uncertainties.

A series of recommendations on the customised design and dimensioning of the ERM has been developed. These specific recommendations summarise the observations obtained through simulations using the simplified model (Task 2.1) and the FEM model (Task 2.2) and will be useful for the development of new material-VOC combinations as well as the characterization of finished prototypes.

The aims of objective 4 have been fully achieved.

6 References

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7 Attachments

7.1 Sensitivity coefficients for Metrological Evaluation

7.1.1 Variation of D_{mat}

We varied the diffusion constant of VOC in ERM D_{mat} , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in **Table 1** in red. The VOC concentration in the chamber, ERM concentration and SEr values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of SEr in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 6**.

Table 6. Variation of D_{mat} .

	Values						
Diffusion constant of VOC in material D_{mat} [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]	10^{-9}	3×10^{-9}	6×10^{-9}	10^{-8}	3×10^{-8}	6×10^{-8}	10^{-7}
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [$10^{-6} \text{ mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$]	5.84	10.2	14.5	18.7	32.4	45.8	57.5
	4.15	7.22	10.2	13.2	22.8	30.4	31.6
	2.94	5.10	7.22	9.32	15.1	14.8	9.68
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$]	944	904	864	825	698	573	452
	921	864	808	752	572	399	250
	889	808	728	649	398	196	76.7
SEr after 7, 14 and 28 days [$10^{-9} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]	19.5	34.1	48.3	62.4	108	153	192
	13.9	24.7	34.2	44.2	76.4	102	105
	9.85	17.1	24.2	31.2	50.7	49.7	32.9
The decrease in SEr over last 14 days [%]	29.1	30.8	29.2	29.4	33.4	51.3	68.7

Figure 4 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying D_{mat} – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 4. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter D_{mat} .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying D_{mat} is graphically shown in **Figures 5** and **6**.

Figure 5. Specific emission rate when varying parameter D_{mat} (linear time scale).

Figure 6. Specific emission rate when varying parameter D_{mat} (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 7 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying D_{mat} .

Figure 7. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter D_{mat} .

7.1.2 Variation of K

We varied the partition coefficient K , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in **Table 1** in red. The VOC concentration in the chamber, ERM concentration and SER values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of SER in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 7**.

Table 7. Variation of K

	Values						
Partition coefficient K [/]	10^{-7}	10^{-6}	10^{-5}	10^{-4}	0.001	0.01	0.1
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-6} mol.m$^{-3}$]	7.28	17.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7
	6.49	12.8	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2
	5.61	9.18	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [mol.m$^{-3}$]	962	868	830	825	824	824	824
	930	798	757	752	752	752	752
	873	697	654	649	649	649	649
SER after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-9} kg.m$^{-2}$s$^{-1}$]	24.4	59.3	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4
	21.8	43.0	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2
	18.8	30.8	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2
The decrease in SER over last 14 days [%]	13.6	28.4	29.4	29.4	29.4	29.4	29.4

Figure 8 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying K – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 8. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter K .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying K is graphically shown in **Figures 9** and **10**.

Figure 9. Specific emission rate when varying parameter K (linear time scale).

Figure 10. Specific emission rate when varying parameter K (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 11 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying K .

Figure 11. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter K .

7.1.3 Variation of c_0

We varied the initial concentration of VOC in ERM c_0 , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in **Table 1** in red. The VOC concentration in the chamber, ERM concentration and *SER* values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of *SER* in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 8**.

Table 8. Variation of c_0

	Values						
Initial concentration in ERM c_0 [mol.m ⁻³]	100	500	800	1000	1300	2500	5000
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [10 ⁻⁶ mol.m ⁻³]	1.87	9.35	15.0	18.7	24.3	46.8	93.5
	1.32	6.60	10.6	13.2	17.2	33.0	66.0
	0.932	4.66	7.45	9.32	12.1	23.3	46.6
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [mol.m ⁻³]	82.5	412	660	825	1070	2060	4120
	75.2	376	602	752	978	1880	3760
	64.9	325	520	649	844	1620	3250
SER after 7, 14 and 28 days [10 ⁻⁹ kg.m ⁻² s ⁻¹]	6.24	31.2	50.0	62.4	81.2	156	312
	4.42	22.1	35.3	44.2	57.4	110	221
	3.12	15.6	25.0	31.2	40.6	78.1	156
The decrease in SER over last 14 days [%]	29.4	29.4	29.2	29.4	29.3	29.6	29.4

Figure 12 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying c_0 – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 12. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter c_0 .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying c_0 is graphically shown in **Figures 13 and 14**.

Figure 13. Specific emission rate when varying parameter c_0 (linear time scale).

Figure 14. Specific emission rate when varying parameter c_0 (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 15 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying c_0 .

Figure 15. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter c_0 .

7.1.4 Variation of d_{air}

We varied the thickness of air layer d_{air} , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in **Table 1** in red. The VOC concentration in the chamber, ERM concentration and *SER* values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of *SER* in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 9**.

Table 9. Variation of d_{air}

	Values						
Thickness of air layer d_{air} [mm]	0.3	1	1.5	2	3	4	5
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-6} mol.m ⁻³]	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7
	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2
	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [mol.m ⁻³]	825	825	825	825	825	825	825
	752	752	752	752	752	753	753
	649	649	649	649	650	650	650
SER after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-9} kg.m ⁻² s ⁻¹]	62.5	62.4	62.5	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4
	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2
	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2
The decrease in SER over last 14 days [%]	29.4						

Figure 16 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying d_{air} – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 16. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter d_{air} .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying d_{air} is graphically shown in **Figures 17** and **18**.

Figure 17. Specific emission rate when varying parameter d_{air} (linear time scale).

Figure 18. Specific emission rate when varying parameter d_{air} (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 19 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying d_{air} .

Figure 19. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter d_{air} .

7.1.5 Variation of D_{air}

We varied the diffusion constant of VOC in air D_{air} , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in **Table 1** in red. The VOC concentration in the

chamber, ERM concentration and *SER* values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of *SER* in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 10**.

Table 10. Variation of D_{air}

	Values						
Diffusion constant of VOC in air D_{air} [$\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.0763	0.1	0.3	0.8
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [$10^{-6} \text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$]	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7
	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2
	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$]	824	824	824	824	824	824	824
	752	752	752	752	752	752	752
	649	649	649	649	649	649	649
SER after 7, 14 and 28 days [$10^{-9} \text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4
	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2
	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2
The decrease in SER over last 14 days [%]	29.4	29.4	29.4	29.4	29.4	29.4	29.4

Figure 20 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying D_{air} – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 20. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter D_{air} .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying D_{air} is graphically shown in **Figures 21** and **22**.

Figure 21. Specific emission rate when varying parameter D_{air} (linear time scale).

Figure 22. Specific emission rate when varying parameter D_{air} (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 23 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying D_{air} .

Figure 23. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter D_{air} .

7.1.6 Variation of V_{ch}

We varied the volume of the chamber V_{ch} , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in Table 1 in red. The VOC concentration in the chamber, ERM concentration and SER values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of SER in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 11**.

Table 11. Variation of V_{ch}

	Values						
Volume of chamber V_{ch} [m ³]	0.005	0.02	0.1	0.27	0.5	1	2
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [10 ⁻⁶ mol.m ⁻³]	1010	253	50.5	18.7	10.1	5.05	2.52
	713	178	35.6	13.2	7.12	3.56	1.78
	504	133	26.7	9.32	5.34	2.67	1.33
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [mol.m ⁻³]	828	825	825	825	825	825	825
	755	753	752	752	752	752	752
	652	650	650	649	649	649	649
SER after 7, 14 and 28 days [10 ⁻⁹ kg.m ⁻² s ⁻¹]	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4
	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2
	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2
The decrease in SER over last 14 days [%]	29.4	29.4	29.2	29.4	29.4	29.4	29.4

Figure 24 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying V_{ch} – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 24. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter V_{ch} .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying V_{ch} is graphically shown in **Figures 25 and 26**.

Figure 25. Specific emission rate when varying parameter V_{ch} (linear time scale).

Figure 26. Specific emission rate when varying parameter V_{ch} (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 27 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying V_{ch} .

Figure 27. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter V_{ch} .

7.1.7 Variation of n_{exch}

We varied the exchange rate of air in the chamber n_{exch} , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in **Table 1** in red. The VOC

concentration in the chamber, ERM concentration and *SER* values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of *SER* in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 12**.

Table 12. Variation of n_{exch}

	Values						
Exchange rate of air in chamber n_{exch} [h^{-1}]	0.05	0.1	0.25	0.5	1	2.5	5
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-6} mol.m $^{-3}$]	200	96.0	37.6	18.7	9.32	3.72	1.86
	136	66.8	26.5	13.2	6.59	2.63	1.32
	94.5	46.9	18.7	9.32	4.66	1.86	0.930
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [mol.m $^{-3}$]	825	825	825	825	825	825	825
	753	752	752	752	752	752	752
	650	650	520	649	649	649	649
SER after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-9} kg.m $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$]	624	624	624	624	624	624	624
	442	442	442	442	442	442	442
	313	313	313	313	313	313	313
The decrease in SER over last 14 days [%]	29.2	29.2	29.2	29.2	29.2	29.2	29.2

Figure 28 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying n_{exch} – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 28. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter n_{exch} .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying n_{exch} is graphically shown in **Figures 29** and **30**.

Figure 29. Specific emission rate when varying parameter n_{exch} (linear time scale).

Figure 30. Specific emission rate when varying parameter n_{exch} (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 31 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying n_{exch} .

Figure 31. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter n_{exch} .

7.1.8 Variation of d_{ERM}

We varied the diameter of the ERM sample d_{ERM} , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in **Table 1** in red. The VOC concentration in the chamber, ERM concentration and SER values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of SER in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 13**.

Table 13. Variation of d_{ERM}

	Values						
Diameter of specimen d_{ERM} [mm]	10	20	30	35	40	50	70
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-6} mol.m ⁻³]	1.53	6.11	13.7	18.7	24.4	38.1	74.6
	1.08	4.31	9.69	13.2	17.2	26.9	52.7
	0.761	3.04	6.85	9.32	12.1	19.0	37.2
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [mol.m ⁻³]	825	825	825	825	825	825	824
	752	752	752	752	752	752	752
	649	649	649	649	649	649	649
SER after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-9} kg.m ⁻² s ⁻¹]	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.3
	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.2	44.1
	31.3	31.3	31.3	31.2	31.2	31.2	31.2
The decrease in SER over last 14 days [%]	29.2	29.2	29.2	29.4	29.4	29.4	29.3

Figure 32 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying d_{ERM} – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 32. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter d_{ERM} .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying d_{ERM} is graphically shown in **Figures 33** and **34**.

Figure 33. Specific emission rate when varying parameter d_{ERM} (linear time scale).

Figure 34. Specific emission rate when varying parameter d_{ERM} (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 35 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying d_{ERM} .

Figure 35. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter d_{ERM} .

7.1.9 Variation of h_{ERM}

We varied the height of the ERM sample h_{ERM} , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in **Table 1** in red. The VOC concentration in the chamber,

ERM concentration and *SER* values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of *SER* in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 14**.

Table 14. Variation of h_{ERM}

	Values						
Height of specimen h_{ERM} [mm]	2	3	4	5	7	10	20
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-6} mol.m ⁻³]	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7
	12.3	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2
	5.81	8.88	9.29	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [mol.m ⁻³]	562	708	781	825	875	912	956
	385	587	690	752	823	876	938
	183	418	562	649	750	825	912
SER after 7, 14 and 28 days [10^{-9} kg.m ⁻² s ⁻¹]	62.3	62.4	62.5	62.4	62.4	62.4	62.4
	41.0	44.1	44.1	44.1	44.1	44.1	44.1
	19.4	29.8	31.2	31.2	31.3	31.3	31.2
The decrease in SER over last 14 days [%]	52.7	32.4	29.3	29.3	29.3	29.3	29.3

Figure 36 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying h_{ERM} – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 36. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter h_{ERM} .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying h_{ERM} is graphically shown in **Figures 37** and **38**.

Figure 37. Specific emission rate when varying parameter h_{ERM} (linear time scale).

Figure 38. Specific emission rate when varying parameter h_{ERM} (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 39 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying h_{ERM} .

Figure 39. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter h_{ERM} .

7.1.10 Variation of M_{VOC}

We varied the molar mass of the VOC M_{VOC} , keeping other parameters constant at the values marked in **Table 1** in red. The VOC concentration in the chamber,

ERM concentration and *SER* values after 7, 14 and 28 days of simulations together with their decrease of *SER* in the last 14 days are presented in **Table 15**.

Table 15. Variation of M_{VOC}

	Values						
Molar mass of VOC $M_{VOC} [g.mol^{-1}]$	20	50	70	86.18	100	120	150
Concentration in chamber after 7, 14 and 28 days [$10^{-6} mol.m^{-3}$]	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7
	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2
	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32	9.32
Concentration in ERM after 7, 14 and 28 days [$mol.m^{-3}$]	825	825	825	825	825	825	825
	752	752	752	752	752	752	752
	649	649	649	649	649	649	649
SER after 7, 14 and 28 days [$10^{-9} kg.m^{-2}s^{-1}$]	14.5	36.2	50.7	62.4	72.5	86.9	109
	10.2	25.6	35.9	44.2	51.3	61.5	76.9
	7.25	18.1	25.4	31.3	36.3	43.5	54.4
The decrease in SER over last 14 days [%]	28.9	29.3	29.2	29.2	29.2	29.3	29.3

Figure 40 presents the concentration of VOC in the chamber during the simulation time when varying M_{VOC} – time is on a logarithmic scale.

Figure 40. The concentration of VOC in the chamber when varying parameter M_{VOC} .

The decrease in the specific emission rate when varying n_{ch} is graphically shown in **Figures 41** and **42**.

Figure 41. Specific emission rate when varying parameter M_{VOC} (linear time scale).

Figure 42. Specific emission rate when varying parameter M_{VOC} (logarithmic time scale).

Figure 43 presents the decrease in the average concentration of VOC in the sample due to its emission into the chamber when varying M_{VOC} .

Figure 43. Average concentration of VOC in the sample when varying parameter M_{VOC} .

7.2 Simulation case studies

The experiments simulated for validation purposes are described in **Table 16**.

Table 16. Simulation case studies

Experiment	Material	VOC	Height of sample [mm]	Diameter of sample [mm]	Duration of experiment [days]	Simulations and comparison performed for [days]	Initial VOC concentration in sample mol.m ⁻³
D9	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	5	36	14	First 7 days	501.2 (0.2195 g, 10 %)
D18	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	2.33	34.5	20	First 7 days	481.5 (0.0904 g, 10 %)
D19	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	3.49	28	20	First 7 days	481.6 (0.0892 g, 10 %)
D22	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	2.34	34.5	20	First 7 days	481.7 (0.0908 g, 10 %)
D28	Beta zeolite (BEA) (powder)	Hexane	2.34	34.5	21	First 7 days	482.9 (0.0910 g, 10 %)

The conditions of the experiments are written in **Table 17**.

Table 17. Experimental conditions with their standard deviations

Experiment	Average T [°C]	Average RH [%]	Average p[kPa]	Air inlet [m ³ /h]	Volume [m ³]
D9	21.36 (±0.2)	50.83 (±0.75)	100.41 (±0.85)	0.5094 (±0.0004)	1.020
D19	24.37 (±0.2)	/	101.00 (±0.91)	0.5022 (±0.0004)	0.270
D18	24.37 (±0.2)	/	101.00 (±0.91)	0.5111 (±0.0004)	0.270

D22	24.37 (± 0.2)	69.85 (± 2.46)	101.01 (± 0.91)	0.5148 (± 0.0004)	0.270
D28	24.34 (± 0.2)	/	100.97 (± 0.61)	0.5467 (± 0.0004)	0.270

Molar mass of hexane $86.18 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. For air diffusivity of hexane, $0.0763 \text{ cm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ was taken. The initial concentration of VOC gases in the chamber was taken as zero in all 3 cases.

7.2.1 Estimation of D_{mat} of references

We varied D_{mat} in numerics and performed a least squared fit for experiment D19 taking 5 points of concentration in the chamber around one week after the start of the measurements (see **Figure 44**).

Figure 44. Regression of the experiment D19 when varying D_{mat} .

The resulting $D_{mat_D19} = 9.46 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

7.2.2 Uncertainty of c_0

Experimentally, the concentration c_0 is calculated based on the mass of the ERM sample, the height of the ERM and the diameter of the ERM. For the calculation of the concentration c_0 , the amount of substance in mol, is calculated using the mass of VOC in the sample, expressed as a function of the loading percentage

and the mass of the emission reference material (m_{ERM}). The mass of VOC is divided by the molecular weight of the VOC of interest and then divided by the ERM volume, expressed as a function of d_{ERM} and h_{ERM} .

The concentration in the sample is expressed as:

$$c_0 = \frac{4m_{ERM}\%L}{\pi d_{ERM}^2 h_{ERM} M_{VOC}}, \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

while the uncertainty can be evaluated as follows:

$$u(c_0) = \sqrt{(u_m \cdot c_m)^2 + (u_{\%L} \cdot c_{\%L})^2 + (u_{h_{ERM}} \cdot c_{h_{ERM}})^2 + (u_{d_{ERM}} \cdot c_{d_{ERM}})^2}. \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

Table 18. Uncertainty budget of the concentration of the sample c_0 for D19 case study.

X	Units X	X	u(X)	u(x) %	(u.C)^2
mERM	g.mol-1	8.9E-01	1.52E-04	0%	6.74E-21
%L	-	10%	6%	60%	8.35E-14
hERM	mm	3	1	0%	1.90E-14
dERM	mm	28	1	30%	1.18E-15
MVOC	g.mol-1	86.18	-	-	-
Co (mol.m-3)		481	322	67%	(k=1)

The propagated uncertainty of the concentration in the sample $u(c_0)$ relative, for experiment D19 is 67% (k=1) (see **Table 18**). The sources of uncertainty are as follows: The contribution of mass of VOC in the ERM (u_m^2) is based on the mass balance manufacturer uncertainty (0.152 mg). The calculation of the contribution of the loading percentage is made on the variability of the impregnation process ($u_{\%L}^2$) (6%). The uncertainty of the sample dimensions: diameter ($u_{d_{ERM}}^2$) and height ($u_{h_{ERM}}^2$) are based on the resolution of the length measurement and the method itself (1 mm). The molecular weight is considered to be constant and its uncertainty is considered negligible.

7.2.3 Uncertainty of D_{mat}

D_{mat} is calculated based on the minimization of the least squares of the difference between the experimental and modelled molar concentration on the chamber at the time equal to 7 days (mol.m⁻³).

The testing of D_{mat} was performed by taking the simplified model as the seed and evaluating the difference between the simulated $C(7 \text{ days})$ and the experimental values. The uncertainty of measured molar concentration in the range used for the regression of D_{mat} , was 1.7 % (k=1). This uncertainty is associated with the method of analysis (GC-MS) and the specific conditions of sampling.

The regression over D_{mat} was performed by testing 18 D_{mat} points. The optimal D_{mat} was the one to provide the best fit of the concentration profile around day 7 of emission. In order to gain an idea about the expected variability of the D_{mat} , several ΔD_{mat} were considered (57 cases) and the resulting ΔC (7 days) was quantified. It was observed that ΔD_{mat} over $8.8e-9 \text{ cm}^2.s^{-1}$ were consistently associated with the ΔC (7 days) higher than the uncertainty value (1.7%; $9.7e-8 \text{ mol.m}^{-3}$ for D19). In order to improve the evaluation of variability, a D_{mat} regression for the 5 experiments simulated was carried out (i.e. D9, D18, D19, D22, D28). The mean value over the five generated D_{mat} values was $1.34e-8 \text{ cm}^2.s^{-1}$ with a standard deviation of $8.7e-9 \text{ cm}^2.s^{-1}$. Based on these evidences, the uncertainty budget of the model includes as uncertainty of D_{mat} , the most conservative value is $8.8e-9 \text{ cm}^2.s^{-1}$. It is worth noting, that the D_{mat} estimate is merely based on the least square evaluation. For the current model, the D_{mat} is considered to be an aggregated (effective) diffusion coefficient, taking into account different transport phenomena within the material, both in the interparticle and intraparticle spaces.

7.3 Evaluation of the controlling step

The evaluation of the controlling step was carried out through the estimation of the Biot number. This topic was described in Deliverable D2. However, for the sake of clarity, and to support the understanding of the recommendations, the method is described again. A higher Biot number is desirable, as it indicates the diffusion is slow enough to control the dynamics of the whole chamber/ERM system.

The Biot number is defined as the ratio between the diffusive and convective resistance, as follows:

$$Bi = \frac{k_c \cdot L_{eq}}{D_{eff}}, \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

where

Bi	Biot number	[adimensional]
k_c	External Mass transfer coefficient	[m min ⁻¹]
D_{eff}	Effective diffusivity	[m ² min ⁻¹]
L_{eq}	Equivalent length of diffusion	[m]

A known diffusion is necessary for the evaluation of the chamber conditions, in terms of controlling phenomenon. For this purpose, a diffusion vial filled with Toluene was selected and used together with the ERM to provide a constant source of VOC that was used as a further indicator of the conditions within the chamber.

7.3.1 Diffusion vial description and design

The dynamic preparation of gas mixtures by diffusion is a suitable method for generating a stable and accurate source of VOCs. The use of diffusion vials with long necks, ensures the controlling transport phenomenon is the Fickian diffusion [7]. The simplicity of this model, makes easier the accurate prediction of the diffusion rate (especially when compared to methods based on other types of diffusion resistance, such as polymeric membranes or films, e.g. [8]).

In any type of diffusion technique, the headspace of the liquid inside the vial provides a constant initial concentration for the diffusion process, which is described by the liquid-vapour equilibrium. Hence, the choice of the expected diffusion rates is a function mainly of the temperature, the VOC species and diffusion resistance. In the case of the vial described in [7], the resistance is defined as a function of the length and the internal diameter of the neck of the diffusion vial.

The diffusion rate within the vial can be known from chamber measurements of concentration but also as a function of the weight loss of the vial due to

evaporation of the VOC. It is recommended that the time interval between weights is 1 week or higher, in order to maintain the uncertainty contribution of mass under negligible levels.